

Ministry of Health

Socio-demographics

1. What is your title?
2. What is your training and education level?
3. How long have you worked in the Ministry of Health?
4. What positions and titles have you had during your career? At which institutions? What types of facilities or institutions are they?

Characteristics of MOH and Neonatal Care

1. What areas, departments, and outcomes are you responsible for in your current role?
2. How would you describe the resources in your country for babies that require NICU / SNCU care at birth?
3. How have availability of neonatal care services changed in your country in the last 10 years? In the last 5 years?
4. What are the biggest challenges your country faces in providing NICU / SNCU care to newborns?
5. How is neonatal health care policy influenced and shaped?
6. What data is collected and fed back to the ministry level? How often is the data collected and is at regional, district, state, or national level?
7. What are the biggest barriers and facilitators to implementing a national policy or strategy for neonatal health?

NICU and SNCU Equipment Procurement & Monitoring

1. Who makes the call on the demand, forecasting and purchases?
2. How do you select the equipment you need? Do the local healthcare providers select the technology or is it mandated from a central authority like WHO or MOH?
3. How timely is procurement? Is purchasing ever an issue?
4. Once equipment is procured, are there protocols for placement logistics, transportation, and installation? Are there challenges with this?
5. Is the equipment locally produced or imported? Do you see a difference between equipment which is locally produced versus imported?
6. Do you accept donated equipment? If equipment is donated, how is it different from what the hospital wants/needs?
7. Are there instances where equipment might be completely replaced instead of spending resources on a repair? When and why?
8. How do you monitor equipment once it's been installed? How do you know when you need to replace equipment? How do you prioritize this?
9. Do you think there is anything that impedes NICU / SNCU work or access because of problems with public perception or lack of information from the health facilities? (Are there any other challenges with Human Resources or resource management that prevents resources from being most effectively used for neonatal care delivery?)
10. Is there a lack of reliable grid power or other infrastructure at or around your NICUs and SNCUs?
11. What is the process for procuring NICU / SNCU equipment spare parts and consumables?

AMC Provider

1. Are you satisfied with AMC (Annual Maintenance Contract) providers serving your facilities?

0 - Other/no response

1 - Very Dissatisfied 2 - Dissatisfied 3 - Neutral 4- Satisfied 5 - Very satisfied

2. Do you have a choice in defining the AMC terms and selecting the AMC provider? If yes, how do you choose? Do AMC providers bid for contracts? How is the AMC provider selected?
3. How do you monitor the AMC's performance? What is the payment schedule? Are there strong incentives for the AMC to provide responsive maintenance? How do you know if they are doing this?
4. How do you perceive the role of the in house biomedical engineer vs the AMC providers' performance?

Recommendations to improve equipment processes:

1. What recommendations do you have for improving the management of lifesaving equipment in the NICU / SNCU?
2. Do you have anything else you would like to add?

Thank you for your participation!